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THE SHORT-WINGED MOLD BEETLES (COLEOPTERA: STAPHYLINIDAE: PSELAPHINAE) OF THE HALYCH NATIONAL PARK

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Krivosheyev, R. E. & Zamoroka, A. M. The short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) of the Halych National Park. Twenty-one species of the Pselaphinae beetles are collected in different localities of Halych National Park (Ukraine, Ivano-Frankivsk Region) in 2011–2013 and 2018. *Bryaxis ullrichii* (Motschulsky, 1851) is recorded for the first time from Ivano-Frankivsk Region.

Key words: Ukraine, Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae, Halytsky National Park.

Кривошесь, Р. Є. і Заморока, А. М. Жуки-потаємці (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) Галицького національного природного парку. — Двадцять один вид жуків-потаємців було знайдено з різних частин Галицького національно-природного парку (Україна, Івано-Франківська область) в 2011–2013 та 2018 роках. Вид *Bryaxis ullrichii* (Motschulsky, 1851) вперше зазначено для Івано-Франківської області.

Ключові слова: Україна, Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae, Галицький національний природний парк.

Introduction

The subfamily Pselaphinae was known to be represented by 126 species of 25 genera in the fauna of Ukraine (Krivosheyev, 2015), especially in its Western part, mainly Carpathians and Transcarpathian region (Roubal, 1930). Although, the Pselaphinae fauna of Dnister River valley and its nearest vicinity is hitherto poorly observed despite a couple of author's publications on the Pselaphines of Dnistrovskiy Canyon National Park in Ternopil Region (Krivosheyev, 2018) and Dnister canyon in Vinnitsia Region (Krivosheyev, 2021). The species *Bryaxis ullrichii* (Motschulsky, 1851) is mentioned for Ukraine (Löbl, 2004) but while studying different publications from Ukraine, this species has not been found in any of them, except Kur-

batov's list of Pselaphinae of the former USSR (Kurbatov, 2007), with no exact locality or reference to material. In 2018, several specimens of were collected near Medynia village along Limnytsya River, near the flooded karst caves in mixed hornbeam-beech forests, and since this species is absent in the species list of the particular region or geographical territory, we herein consider *B. ullrichii* to be recorded for Ivano-Frankivsk Region for the first time. Also, the Pselaphinae list contains species deposited in the entomological collection of Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University (PUIF), and some specimens from State Museum of Natural History in Lviv (SMNHL). The specimens collected by the authors, are deposited in Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology in Kyiv (SIZK).

Euplectus nanus Reichenbach, 1816

Winkler, 1925: 452; Roubal, 1930: 494; Löbl, 2004: 285.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Kasowa Hora near Burshtyn, 4.11.1893, 1 specimen (SMNHL).

Distribution. Central and Eastern Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Under the bark and occasionally in litter, often with ants (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Euplectus brunneus Grimmer, 1841

Winkler, 1925: 450; Roubal, 1930: 493; Löbl, 2004: 284

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: mixed forest near Medynia village, in dead wood, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Under the bark and in dead wood, often with ants (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Trimium brevicorne (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler, 1925: 449; Roubal, 1930: 490; Löbl, 2004: 293.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 2 specimens, 1.09.2018, 7 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 7 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Halych, deciduous forest, 11.07.2013, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Dubivtsi village, in litter, 49.088246, 24.809020, 12.07.2013, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. almost whole Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In moss and litter, sometimes under the bark, in all types of forests (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Trimium carpathicum Saulcy, 1875

Winkler, 1925: 449; Roubal, 1930: 491; Löbl, 2004: 294.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 2 specimens, 1.09.2018, 6 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Dubivtsi village, in litter, 49.088246, 24.809020, 12.07.2013, 11 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Halych, deciduous forest, 11.07.2013, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Eastern Europe and Balkans (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of the beech forests (Roubal, 1930).

Brachygluta fossulata (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler, 1925: 455 Roubal, 1930: 500; Löbl, 2004: 297.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Halych, the bank of Dnister river, 49.127956, 24.723667, 9.07.2013, 1 specimen, 24.09.2012, 1 specimen (Zamoroka) (PUIF).

Distribution. Europe excl. France, Romania, Spain and Portugal (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of all moist forests, along riverbanks and in grass, sometimes under the bark (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Brachygluta haematica (Reichenbach, 1816)

Winkler, 1925: 455; Roubal, 1930: 501; Löbl, 2004: 297.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Halych, the bank of Dnister river, 49.127956, 24.723667, 9.07.2013, 19 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 4 ♂, 4 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe excl. France, Romania, Spain and Portugal (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of the deciduous forests, under the stones and in grass of meadows, in the sand along the freshwater and sometimes halophyllic basins (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Brachygluta simplicior Raffray, 1904

Löbl, 2004: 299.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 3 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. West and South of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In grass and moss in the meadows and near the freshwater basins (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis carinula (Rey, 1888)

Winkler, 1925: 460; Löbl, 2004: 304.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 1 ♀, 1.09.2018, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Central Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Thermophilic species living in forest litter, cliff slopes and under the stones (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis puncticollis (Denny, 1825)

Winkler, 1925: 460; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 309.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Halych, deciduous forest, 11.07.2013, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost the whole Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter, in dead wood and in moss of the deciduous forests (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis nigripennis (Aubé, 1844)

Winkler, 1925: 459; Roubal, 1930: 502; Löbl, 2004: 308.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 4 ♂, 6 ♀, 1.09.2018, 13 ♂, 16 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 5 ♂, 5 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Halych, deciduous forest, 11.07.2013, 2 ♂,

3 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Dubivtsi village, in litter, 49.088246, 24.809020, 12.07.2013, 3 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. The whole Europe except North (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Mountain species living in litter of beech forests, in dead wood and under the stones (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995)

Bryaxis frivaldskyi (Reitter, 1887)

Winkler, 1925: 462; Roubal, 1930: 505; Löbl, 2004: 305.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 1.09.2018, 3 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine, Poland, Hungaria and Slovenia (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of mountain forests (Roubal, 1930).

Bryaxis ruthenus (Saulcy, 1877)

Winkler, 1925: 462; Roubal, 1930: 507; Löbl, 2004: 310.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 1 ♂, 5 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine, Romania, Poland, Slovakia, and Italy (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter and under the bark on the mountain slopes in deciduous and coniferous forests (Roubal, 1930).

Bryaxis carpathicus (Saulcy, 1875)

Winkler, 1925: 462; Roubal, 1930: 505; Löbl, 2004: 304.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine, Poland, Slovakia, Romania, Serbia (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Mountain species lives in litter of the beech forests (Roubal, 1930).

Bryaxis curtisii (Leach, 1817)

Winkler, 1925: 462; Roubal, 1930: 505; Löbl, 2004: 305.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 3 ♂, 2 ♀, 1.09.2018, 13 ♂, 13 ♀; mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 3 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Halych, deciduous forest, 11.07.2013, 7 ♂, 4 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Dubivtsi village, in litter, 49.088246, 24.809020, 12.07.2013, 7 ♂, 4 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Halych, soil traps near the National Park office, 24.09.2012, 1 ♂, experimental squares in the steppe, 15.06.2012, 1 ♂ (Zamoroka) (PUIF); soil traps near Tsenzliv village, fir forest, “Hlynianyi lis” tract, 15–30.06.2011, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, in the ravine, 15–31.07.2011, 1 ♀; 1–15.09.2011, 3 ♂; 1–15.07.2011, 1 ♂ (Zamoroka) (PUIF).

Distribution. Europe excluding North (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Common species living in litter and under the bark in all deciduous and mixed forests (Roubal, 1930).

Bryaxis clavicornis (Panzer, 1809)

Winkler, 1925: 461; Roubal, 1930: 504; Löbl, 2004: 304.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 1.09.2018, 3 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 3 ♂, 13 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Halych, soil traps near the National Park office, 24.09.2012, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Zamoroka) (PUIF); soil traps near Tsenzliv village, fir forest, “Hlynianyi lis” tract, 15–30.06.2011, 1 ♂, in the ravine, 15–31.07.2011, 1 ♂ (Zamoroka) (PUIF).

Distribution. Central Europe, Norway and Italy (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter and moss, often on the riverbanks and in dead wood (Roubal, 1930).

Bryaxis ullrichii (Motchulsky, 1851) (Figs 1–2)

Winkler, 1925: 460; Löbl, 2004: 311.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 4 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Eastern and South-Eastern Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of the moist deciduous forests (personal observations).

Figs 1–2. *Bryaxis ullrichii*: 1 — habitus, dorsal; 2 — aedeagus.

Bryaxis reitteri (Saulcy, 1875)

Winkler, 1925: 461; Roubal, 1930: 505; Löbl, 2004: 309.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 10.07.2013, 1 ♀, 1.09.2018, 10 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 5 ♂, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); soil traps near Tsenzhiv village, fir forest, “Hlynianyi lis” tract, 15-30.06.2011, 1 ♂ (Zamoroka) (PUIF).

Distribution. Ukraine, Slovakia, Poland and Romania (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Mountain species living in litter of beech and fir forests (Roubal, 1930).

Bythinus burrellii Denny, 1825

Winkler, 1925: 462; Roubal, 1930: 507; Löbl, 2004: 311.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Halych, deciduous forest, 11.07.2013, 2 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. North, Center and East of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of the deciduous forests along the riverbanks (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bythinus macropalpus Aubé, 1833

Winkler, 1925: 462; Roubal, 1930: 507; Löbl, 2004: 312.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Karst beech forest near Temyrivtsi village, in litter, 49.122981, 24.573316, 1.09.2018, 2 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe excl. South (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In grass, moss and litter of the flooded forests and meadows (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Tychus niger (Paykull, 1800)

Winkler, 1925: 465; Roubal, 1930: 508; Löbl, 2004: 320.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Mixed forest near Medynia village, in litter, 49.067614, 24.546257, 25–30.08.2018, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of the dry deciduous and mixed forests, in moss and under the stones (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Pselaphus heisei (Herbst, 1792)

Winkler, 1925: 466; Roubal, 1930: 508; Löbl, 2004: 327.

Material examined. Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk: Halych, soil traps near the National Park office, 24.09.2012, 1 specimen, soil traps along the fields on the remains of beech forest, 17.05.2012, 1 specimen; soil traps Hora Vynohrad near Tustan village, steppe, 18.06.2012, 1 specimen; soil traps near Tsenzhiv village, fir forest, “Hlynianyi lis” tract, 15-30.06.2011, 1 specimen (Zamoroka) (PUIF).

Distribution. Almost whole Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter, dead wood, anthills, grass, moss and under the bark (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

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